

REVIEW: *STORIES OF MY LIFE AND HOME* BY

'JAM DBYANGS BKRA SHIS འཇམ་དབྱངས་བཀྲ་ཤིས།

Reviewed by Lugyal Bum (Klu rgyal 'bum ལུགཡལ་བུམ། Lijiaben 李加本)*

'Jam dbyangs bkra shis འཇམ་དབྱངས་བཀྲ་ཤིས།. 2021. *Stories of My Life and Home*. 2 maps, 23 B&W illustrations. Amazon KDP. <https://tinyurl.com/2xxp5snz>. 137pp. ISBN-13, 979-8470433923, ASIN B09FCFP2FL (paperback 5.68USD).

Stories of My Life and Home features twenty-two narratives of memories, magic realism, and experiences rooted in Tibetan traditional pastoral life as it rapidly transitions from tent-living to permanent housing with easy access to urban settings and emerging new digital technologies. 'Jam dbyangs bkra shis's (b. 1994) collection is mostly based in Mdo ba (Duowa) Town, Reb gong (Tongren) County, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China, and on his continuing multifaceted life journey and experiences with education.

Daily communication with his family in 'A Day' and on pilgrimage ('My First Pilgrimage') with his maternal grandmother when he was very young depicts 'Jam dbyangs in a close relationship with his family members. How will urbanization and modernization influence such family relationships?

Born in a family of yak and sheep herders, 'Jam dbyangs began tending his family's sheep at age six. At age eleven, an attempt was made to enroll him in a local government primary school. His father was critical of such education and had resisted 'Jam dbyangs' earlier pleas to attend school, reminiscent of Tara Westover's experiences as recounted in *Educated: A Memoir*. Later, when 'Jam dbyangs' father relented and took him to enroll, he could not register because his name was absent from the family's *hukou*

* Lugyal Bum (Klu rgyal 'bum, Lijiaben). 2023. Review: *Stories of My Life and Home* by 'Jam dbyangs bkra shis. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 63:491-494.

'official registration document'. His family had deliberately not included him to avoid fines under the One Child Policy.

The following year, 'Jam dbyangs' parents and paternal grandmother escorted him to Bla brang Monastery to become a monk. After seven years of Tibetan monastic education, he became a layman and attended private schools in Mtsho sngon and Lha sa to study Chinese and English.

The book features a preface (by filmmaker Khashen Gyal) and the author's introduction, followed by five themed sections that the author describes as:

The first three are about culture and religion, including demons, ghosts, and deities. ... Part Four concerns social issues created by social media. Part Five consists of stories related to my friends, my family members, and myself (17).

These materials offer an understanding of 'Jam dbyangs' life with his family and community. A recurrent theme is how lives are affected by the supernatural, vividly illustrated by three stories in Part One that retell his grandfather's (1940-2022) stories. Ghosts and demons seem real, given the cultural context. For example, 'A Demon Monk' describes how a monk became a demon after abandoning his religious practice and endangering local monasteries, exemplifying how hatred and regret transform men into evil entities while foreshadowing the author's bizarre night experience in a hotel ('Room 204').

Part Two continues with supernatural experiences. 'The Power of Belief' and 'A Marriage' deal with marriage and supernatural beings reflecting the role of power and wealth in marriage. The third story in Part Two, 'The Sickness Causing Demon', involves seeking a demon that causes sickness and finding and killing it.

Part Three stories are associated with historical events, consequences of inappropriate religious rituals, and the power of an amulet. Before 1950, many Tibetans suffered from the rule of Ma Bufang (1903-1975). For example:

In the late 1920s and the early 1930s, Ma Bufang launched seven expeditions into the Golog region of Tibet, slaughtering ethnic

Tibetans and destroying Tibetan Buddhist temples in Tibet as well as in his home province of Qinghai (<https://bit.ly/3weCsol> 19 August 2022).

A Tibetan man in 'The Power of Religion' ended his life for defending Bla brang Monastery and its monks from Ma Bufang's violence. It seems he was committed to chasing and destroying the enemies who attacked the monastery, even if it meant he might lose his life. The second story, 'A *Lha Ba*' demonstrates a family's chronic misfortunes from not regularly making offerings to mountain deities.

"An Amulet" stresses the power of an amulet, the value of wearing one, and what may happen when it is lost, leaving its owner unprotected, e.g., a notorious bandit loses his amulet and is quickly killed.

Part Four features real-life stories of Tibetan nomads, inappropriate education, and the impact of rapidly changing digital technology. Urbanization and economic development encouraging people to have a town/city life since at least about 2010, have encouraged Tibetan herders to move to urban areas where they lack the requisite skills to subsist. 'Moving & A Story' describes such a family and related challenges.

Digital media is a convenient tool offering new forms of communication and entertainment, but it is a double-edged sword, destroying lives when misused. Broken marriages and families in 'WeChat Crimes,' addiction to video games, and bad tempers in 'WeChat Games' and 'Darling Child' are examples of sad outcomes.

'Jam dbyangs shares his unusual education journey and life transitions from child to respected monk to layman in 'Karma', critically reflecting that in the eyes of local Tibetans, what he wears matters more than the person.

In Part Five, the narrator follows a *bla ma's* advice and attends a private school in Lha sa where a friend drowns in a local river ('My Dear Friend'), an experience that continues to haunt, reemerging in "Room 204."

I recommend this collection of stories to anyone interested in learning more about supernatural beings and ghosts in the Tibetan cultural context and how urban development and advanced

digital technology impact contemporary Tibetan society. Recent transformations in Tibetan society are rarely presented in stories, thus providing an opportunity to grasp aspects of such changes from a young man's experience.

REFERENCE

Westover, Tara. 2018. *Educated: A Memoir*. New York: Random House.

TIBETAN TERMS

'jam dbyangs འཇམ་དབྱངས།

'jam dbyangs bkra shis

འཇམ་དབྱངས་བཀྲ་ཤིས།

Khashen Gyal, mkha' byams

rgyal མཁའ་བྱམས་རྒྱལ།

lha sa ལྷ་ས།

Lugyal Bum, klu rgyal 'bum

ལུགལ་བུམ་ལུ་རྒྱལ་པུམ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།

CHINESE TERMS

Duowa 多哇

hukou 户口

Lijiaben 李加本

Tongren 同仁